

Approaches to Quantifying the Role of Nature for Tourists Using Social Media Data – From Regional to Global Scales

Matti Hästbacka*, Tatu Leppämäki*, Tuuli Toivonen*

* Digital Geography Lab, University of Helsinki

Abstract. Nature-based tourism is a rapidly growing subsector of the global tourism industry. Traditional data sources often fall short in capturing the full scope of nature's importance to tourists. This paper presents ways of quantifying nature's importance to tourists at regional and global scales. By employing place-based, content-based, and user-based analyses, the research highlights the overarching importance of nature for tourists while uncovering varying geographic patterns. The findings underscore the crucial role of nature in tourism and the potential of social media data to inform tourism and conservation planning.

Keywords. nature-based tourism, big data, social media

1. Introduction

The travel and tourism sector is one of the largest and fastest growing global industries, corresponding to an estimated 10 % of global GDP in 2019 (WTTC, 2022). Nature-based tourism is a rapidly growing subsector of the international tourism industry, with increasing interest trends being reported globally (Waldron et al., 2020) as well as in established beach tourism destinations such as the Canary Islands (Hästbacka et al., 2024).

While the importance of nature as an attractor in tourism is broadly recognised, an understanding of the spatial patterns of nature-based tourism remains more limited, both in individual destinations and globally. Information about tourism flows is traditionally collected at ports of entry and exit. While these methods provide useful information about tourists' mobilities and preferences, they may not adequately capture important aspects of their in-destination mobilities.

Published in "Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)", edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15351303>
© Authors 2025. CC BY 4.0 License.

Over the past decade, mobile big data, such as social media data have emerged as a promising source of information for understanding people's mobility patterns across different scales. Here, we present preliminary findings from ongoing work in measuring the role of nature for tourists using geotagged Flickr posts at the regional scale in the Canary Islands, and at the global scale.

2. Different Perspectives to Quantifying the Role of Nature at the Regional Scale

We downloaded 723,012 geotagged Flickr posts (394,295 with images) posted between 2004 and 2023. We used protected area (UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, 2023) and land cover classification data (European Environment Agency, 2019) to produce a classification with four categories of 'nature': Protected areas, other areas of high biodiversity value, non-protected nature, and other areas.

2.1. Place-Based Perspective

By analysing the spatial distribution of Flickr posts by land use, we found that 31.7% of posts were taken in nature and 24.3% in protected areas, with significant variation between the islands.

2.2. Content-Based Perspective

We used a semantic clustering approach (Väisänen et al., 2021) in combination with HDBSCAN (McInnes et al., 2017) to automatically identify thematic patterns in the image data. We detected 31 semantically coherent clusters overall. Nature-related clusters comprised 25.9% of the total content, but the largest cluster consisted of photos of humans, across all land uses and islands. We found that a large share of nature-related posts was taken outside areas classified as nature.

2.3. User-Based Perspective

By analysing users' spatial behaviour, we found that 61.8% of Flickr users posted at least once from nature, and 46.8% from protected areas. Significant differences were found in nature visitation patterns among tourists from different countries. Similarly, we found the relative importance of nature-related contents to vary significantly between tourists based on their country of origin.

3. Towards Mapping Global Patterns of Nature-Based Tourism

Using a global database of geotagged Flickr posts published between 2010 and 2024, we quantified the transnational mobility flows of 345,922 Flickr users with reported home locations. We then compared these origin-destination flows to official tourism statistics to understand how well Flickr represents ‘real’ tourist mobilities. By analysing the spatial behaviour of users abroad (that is, outside of their reported home countries), we then computed multiple indicators for measuring the importance of nature for different sending and receiving countries. Preliminary results indicate that Flickr reflects patterns in official tourism statistics. In addition, the importance of nature in tourism varies significantly based on the origin and destination of tourism flows.

4. Conclusion

The findings presented here confirm nature's significant role in tourism and emphasise the need to understand geographic variation in people's interest towards visiting nature. As nature-based tourism grows, pressures on natural areas are likely to increase, necessitating informed conservation planning. Owing to a unique combination of high spatiotemporal accuracy and global coverage, social media data approaches provide a flexible way to measure human mobility on multiple scales. Social media data continues to be a promising source of information for reconciling the often-conflicting goals of nature-based recreation and the conservation of biodiversity.

References

- European Environment Agency. (2019). *CORINE Land Cover 2018 (vector), Europe, 6-yearly—Version 2020_20u1, May 2020* (Version 20.01) [FGeo,Spatialite]. European Environment Agency. <https://doi.org/10.2909/71C95A07-E296-44FC-B22B-415F42ACDF0>
- Hästbacka, M., Brias Guinart, A., Eklund, J., González Hernández, M. M., Leppämäki, T., Morales González, S. D. C., Pulido Hernández, M.,

- Ramirez Cabrera, A. S., Santana Suárez, A., & Toivonen, T. (2024). *Changes in nature-based tourism and outdoor recreation in the Canary Island: Observations, information needs and ways forward*. University of Helsinki, Digital Geography Lab. <https://doi.org/10.31885/2024.062702>
- McInnes, L., Healy, J., & Astels, S. (2017). hdbscan: Hierarchical density based clustering. *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 2(11), 205. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00205>
- UNEP-WCMC, & IUCN. (2023). *Protected Planet: The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) [Online], June 2024, Cambridge, UK: UNEP-WCMC and IUCN. Available at: Www.protectedplanet.net. [Dataset]. www.protectedplanet.net. www.protectedplanet.net.*
- Väisänen, T., Heikinheimo, V., Hiippala, T., & Toivonen, T. (2021). Exploring human–nature interactions in national parks with social media photographs and computer vision. *Conservation Biology*, 35(2), 424–436. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13704>
- Waldron, A., Adams, V., Allan, J., Arnell, A., Abrantes, J. P., Asner, G., Atkinson, S., Baccini, A., Jonathan, E M Baillie, Balmford, A., J Austin, Brander, L., Brondizio, E., Bruner, A., Neil, K Burkart, Butchart, S., Rio, ... Yp Zhang. (2020). *Protecting 30 percent of the planet: Costs, benefits and economic implications*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19950.64327>

WTTC. (2022). *Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2022*.

<https://wttc.org/Portals/0/Documents/Reports/2022/EIR2022-Global%20Trends.pdf>